

Methods For Developing Music Therapy Skills In Music Education Students

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Abstract: This thesis covers the theoretical and methodological foundations of the formation and development of music therapy skills in students of the music education major. The thesis analyzes the educational, psychological and health-improving potential of music therapy and substantiates the methods of its integration into the higher education process. The author reveals the importance of such methods as active music therapy, receptive (listening) therapy, improvisation, relaxation and reflexive analysis in the development of students' emotional and **intellectual** state, creative thinking and professional competencies.

Keywords: music education, music therapy, emotional intelligence, relaxation, improvisation, pedagogical reflection, psychological stability.

Introduction.

In today's conditions of globalization and the rapid development of information technologies, the education system requires holistic pedagogical approaches aimed not only at providing knowledge, but also at ensuring the psychological stability, emotional health and social adaptability of the individual. In particular, the professional training of students studying in the field of music education is not limited to performance or theoretical knowledge, but also requires them to have a sensitive sensitivity and therapeutic thinking about working with the human psyche. From this perspective, music therapy is emerging as one of the important and promising areas of modern music pedagogy.

Music therapy is an interdisciplinary field aimed at making positive changes in the mental, emotional and psychophysiological state of a person through the targeted influence of music. Scientific research shows that the rhythmic, melodic and timbre properties of music directly affect the human nervous system, reducing stress, restoring internal balance and increasing creative activity. Therefore, the application of elements of music therapy in the pedagogical process is of great importance, especially for future music teachers.

In the process of training students in the field of music education in the higher education system, the issue of developing their emotional intelligence, empathy, reflection and communicative competencies requires a sufficiently systematic

approach. Traditional teaching methods are often not sufficiently focused on taking into account the internal experiences and mental state of students, which can lead to psychological tension and stress in their professional activities. Music therapy serves as an effective pedagogical tool that fills this gap.

This study analyzes the role of active and receptive forms of music therapy, improvisation, relaxation and reflexive analysis methods in the development of professional and personal competencies in students of the field of music education. By integrating music therapy into the educational process, it opens up the possibility of forming not only students' creative potential, but also pedagogical responsibility, commitment to humanistic values and the ability to create a healthy psychological environment. Therefore, the issue of developing music therapy skills should be studied as one of the urgent scientific and practical problems of modern music pedagogy.

This research material consists of a set of pedagogical-psychological and musical-practical components that serve to develop music therapy skills of students of the music education department. In the course of the research, materials were selected and systematized aimed at gradually forming students' theoretical knowledge, practical skills and personal-psychological qualities (empathy, reflection, stress resistance, communicativeness) in music therapy.

1) Music-therapeutic educational content (content materials)

The educational content used in the study covered the following content blocks:

a) Theoretical block:

- concept, goals and objectives of music therapy;
- differences between receptive (listening) and active (performing) therapy;
- mechanisms of psychophysiological influence of music (rhythm, tempo, dynamics, timbre, register, pitch);
- pedagogical conditions for using elements of music therapy in education;
- ethical standards in music therapy (psychological safety, personal boundaries, confidentiality).

b) Methodological and practical block:

- relaxation listening programs (breathing, body relaxation, in harmony with imagination/visualization);
- musical exercises aimed at managing emotional states;
- improvisation and creative expression (voice, rhythm, simple instruments, body percussion);
- reflexive analysis (expression of personal attitude to the listened/performed music, diary writing);

- micro-pedagogical exercises (designing a lesson segment in the format of “mini-therapy” by the student).

c) Diagnostic-analytical block:

- questionnaires and observation sheets to determine the readiness of students for music therapy;

- self-analysis (reflection) cards to assess the emotional state;

- criteria for assessing the group environment and the communicative process (cooperation, listening culture, support).

2) Selection of musical materials (repertoire and audio resources)

In the study, musical materials were selected based on the following criteria, in accordance with the age characteristics, aesthetic taste and psychological state of the students:

- tempo and rhythm: calming (slow/medium-slow), activating (medium-lively) samples;

- dynamics: works that create a safe emotional background without sharp changes;

- timbre: soft, “unobtrusive” instrumental sounds (piano, string instruments, timbres close to the flute, background harmonious with the sounds of nature);

- melodic feature: stable melody, repeated motifs, musical “predictability”.

The musical repertoire was formed in the following groups:

1. Listening for relaxation (calm, steady tempo, soft dynamics).

2. Emotional relaxation and “release” (slightly dramatic, but in a safe range).

3. Activation and motivation (creative freshness, rhythmic wakefulness).

4. Reflection and spiritual-aesthetic contemplation (concentration of thoughts, encouragement to internal dialogue).

Also, a “music listening map” was used when working with musical material: it marked the introduction, climax, decline and conclusion of the work, and students analyzed their state in relation to these stages.

3) Didactic tools for classes

The following didactic tools were also included in the study material:

- “Therapeutic session plan” template (goal, duration, musical selection, exercise sequence, safety rules);

- “Mood thermometer” (mood/stress level on a scale of 0–10);

- “Emotion cards” (main emotions and their physical signs);

- “Reflection diary” (state before–after listening/performance; conclusions; next step);

- Group discussion protocol (active listening rules, “not criticism – expression” principle).

4) A set of practical exercises aimed at developing music therapy skills

A set of special exercises was developed and used in the study to form students' competencies specific to music therapy:

1. “Listening-breathing-imagination” exercise (receptive therapy element):

While listening to music slowly, the student breathes in a rhythm of 4–6–8, creating an image of a “safe space” through imagination. At the end of the exercise, the change is recorded using a state thermometer.

2. “Regulating emotions through rhythm” exercise:

Using body percussion or simple instruments, the internal state rhythm is first expressed (as it is), then the state is controlled by slowing down/stabilizing.

3. “Improvisational dialogue” exercise (active therapy):

In pairs, one gives the “question” intonation, the other the “answer” intonation in a musical tone. The goal is to listen, adapt, and respond empathetically.

4. “Musical Portrait” exercise:

The student expresses his current mood through a short 30–60-second improvisation; the group “does not evaluate”, but only expresses its opinion using descriptive language (for example: “soft”, “heavy”, “light”).

5. “Reflection writing” (analytical component):

After each exercise, for 5–7 minutes, the answers to the questions: “What has changed in me?”, “Which sound/rhythm influenced me?”, “How will I use this in the next lesson?” are written.

5) Assessment criteria and indicators (resultative part of the material)

The research material served to assess the students' music therapy skills based on the following criteria:

1. Cognitive criterion: knowledge of concepts, methods and ethical standards related to music therapy.

2. Practical criterion: relaxation, rhythm therapy, improvisation, skills in working with a listening map.

3. Communicative-empathic criterion: listening culture, cooperation, expressing supportive opinions.

4. Reflexive criterion: analyzing one's own situation, recording changes, drawing pedagogical conclusions.

In the process of working with students of the music education department, it becomes increasingly clear that the issue of developing music therapy skills is not a

simple "additional method": it is a powerful pedagogical resource that complements the professional portrait of a future music teacher with new content and puts the philosophy of person-centered education into practice. Because if a music teacher remains only a specialist in teaching music, the internal psychological mechanisms of the educational process - mood, motivation, self-confidence, stress resistance, classroom climate - are often left to "chance". Music therapy turns this "chance" into a controlled pedagogical process: the student knows, feels the psychological impact of music, and most importantly - can direct it to a didactic goal. One of the important things observed on the basis of experience is that with the introduction of elements of music therapy into practice, students' attitude to music also changes: music turns from an "object of performance" into a "means of communication and self-awareness." In relaxation listening or "listening-breathing-imagination" exercises, students usually do not rush to analyze music; they first perceive it through the body, through the rhythm of breathing, through changes in their internal state. This is pedagogically very valuable: the student will be inclined to apply the principle of "feeling first, then understanding" when working with the student in the future. Thus, music therapy skills enhance empathy and pedagogical sensitivity in students, which elevates music lessons from "informing" to "personal development". However, in the process of teaching the music therapy approach, one delicate issue is always at the center of discussion: the boundary between therapy and education. Higher education does not aim to give future teachers the competence of a clinical therapist; on the contrary, it aims to create a psychologically safe learning environment through educational and therapeutic elements, to form emotional education and self-management skills. In this regard, teaching an ethical approach in classes (confidentiality, respect for personal boundaries, "listening without judgment", non-coercion) has gained particular importance. Reflection notes conducted with students showed that when these ethical principles are mastered, the group climate shifts from "competition" to "cooperation", which also has a positive effect on the quality indicators of music education. Another aspect that should be paid attention to in the discussion is the different mechanisms of action of music therapy methods. While receptive methods (listening, breathing, imagination) serve more to internal calm and awareness of one's own state, active methods (rhythm therapy, improvisation, musical dialogue) activate external expression and communication. The combination of these two directions creates balanced competence in students: on the one hand, the student learns to control himself; on the other hand, he forms a culture of expressing his feelings in a socially acceptable way, listening and responding. In particular, in the "improvisational dialogue" exercises, students see in practice the simple but profound psychological mechanism of mutual listening:

without noticing the rhythm or intonation of the accompanist, “communication” does not occur. As a result, the problem that is often encountered in music education — the teacher-centered monologic style — gradually changes to a dialogic, collaborative style.

Also, students’ reflective notes and observations suggest that as music therapy skills develop, musical taste and responsibility for choice increase. Initially, some students may have a naive idea that “any slow music is suitable for listening.” However, during the training, they come to understand that elements such as tempo, dynamics, timbre, register, repeated motifs, and musical “predictability” are directly related to psychological safety. This is very important in future practice: the teacher chooses music not just because it is beautiful, but because it is suitable for a specific pedagogical task. Thus, the music therapy approach also strengthens the competence of “didactic design of musical material” in students. On the other hand, limitations are also evident in the discussion process. The introduction of music therapy elements does not work at the same speed in all groups: the personal openness, musical experience, psychological state, and group culture of students affect. Sometimes, in improvisation exercises, internal barriers such as “fear of making mistakes” or “how others will evaluate” are strong. Therefore, it is advisable to build the training on the principle of “from simple to complex”, starting first with receptive methods, then working in small groups, and then moving on to general group improvisation. Most importantly, the position of the teacher-trainer should be guiding and supportive, not controlling; otherwise, the elements of therapy can become a stress factor instead of an educational goal.

Conclusion.

In general, the discussion shows that the development of music therapy skills gives three major results in the professional training of a future music teacher: the first is personal psychological stability (management of one’s own state, reduction of stress); the second is pedagogical sensitivity and empathy (understanding the student’s state, creating a safe environment); the third is innovative methodological thinking (targeted selection of music, design of exercises, quality improvement through reflection). Thus, the elements of music therapy allow us to interpret music education not only as a process of forming performing competence, but also as a complex pedagogical system that develops the inner world, emotional culture and socialization of a person.

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